

Multimetal multiligand complex formation equilibria of copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) with L-2-amino-3-methylbutanoic acid (valine) and nitrilotriacetic acid

V. Shankar, G. K. Mishra and V. Krishna*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Formation equilibria of homo and heterobinuclear ternary/quaternary complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with nitrilotriacetic acid (A) and valine (B) ligands in aqueous solution have been investigated. Stability constants of the complexes and the complex formation equilibria at temperature 30 ± 1° and the ionic strength I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) have been determined by potentiometric method. Complexes of the type MAB (2 : 2 : 1) and M₁M₂AB (1 : 1 : 1 : 1)/(1 : 1 : 2 : 1) have been discussed from the computer based analysis. Stability constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes follow the Irving-Williams order.

Keywords : Multimetal multiligand complexes, ternary complexes, quaternary complexes.

In continuation of our studies on the formation equilibria of metal complexes¹, in this paper we have described formation of valine and nitrilotriacetic acid complexes of the metal ions, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} respectively.

Results and discussion

The ligand NTA behaves as a tetradentate ligand, coordinating through a nitrogen and three carboxyl oxygen atoms. The secondary ligand valine functions as a bidentate ligand and coordinates through nitrogen and carboxyl group. Proton ligand stability constants obtained for both the ligands are presented in Table 1, which are in good agreement with literature values².

The formation of quaternary complexes in an aqueous solution may be conveniently expressed by the equilibrium :

The overall stability constant is given by :

$$\beta_{pqrst} = \frac{[(M_1)_p(M_2)_q(A)_r(B)_s(OH)_t]}{[M_1]^p [M_2]^q [A]^r [B]^s [OH]^t}$$

where the stoichiometric numbers p, q, r, s are either zero or positive integer and t is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a neutral species.

Table 1. Stability constants and other related constants of binary, ternary and quaternary complexes of nitrilotriacetic acid (A) and valine (B) with different metal ions in aqueous solution at 30 ± 1°, I = 0.1 M NaNO₃

(a) Proton ligand formation constants (log β _{oorst}) of the ligands			
NTA	AH ₃	AH ₂	AH
log β	14.98	12.90	9.95
Valine	-	BH ₂	BH
log β	-	11.75	9.48
(b) Hydrolytic constants (log β _{poort}) of metal ions			
	Ni	Cu	Zn
M(OH) ⁺	-8.10	-6.29	-7.89
M(OH) ₂	-16.87	-13.10	-14.92
(c) Stability constants (log β _{porst}) of binary complexes			
	Ni	Cu	Zn
MA	10.43	11.96	10.10
MA ₂	16.34	17.51	14.26
MA(OH)	-	4.53	3.56
MB	5.82	8.71	4.61
(d) Stability constants (log β _{porst}) of ternary complexes			
	Ni	Cu	Zn
MAB	15.75	19.73	14.70
M ₂ A ₂ B	29.12	31.58	28.18
(e) Stability constants (log β _{pqrst}) of quaternary complexes			
	Cu-Zn	Cu-Ni	Zn-Ni
M ₁ M ₂ AB	24.46	24.49	23.50
M ₁ M ₂ A ₂ B	34.0	36.00	32.25
Limits of error in the constants ± (0.1 ~ 0.2) in log unit			

The numerical refinement is consistent with the following species in calculating the metal ligand binary stability constants of $M^{2+} : A$ (1 : 1/1 : 2) and $M^{2+} : B$ (1 : 1) system.

Only MA, MA₂ and MB types of binary species have been detected in addition to AH₃, AH₂, AH and BH₂, BH species in the above mentioned binary systems.

Moreover (CuAOH) and (ZnAOH) species is also identifiable at pH ~5.8 and ~6.0.

The distribution curves indicate the formation of [MAB]²⁻ which is supposed to exist in the ratio 1 : 1 : 1 along with the binary species in the pH range 3.0 to 8.0 according to equilibria :

The homobinuclear ternary species [M₂A₂B]³⁻ have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria of 2 : 2 : 1 M²⁺ : A : B systems, species distribution curves of [M₂A₂B]³⁻ suggest the formation of binuclear complex in the pH range ~4.0-9.0 according to equilibria :

The speciation curves indicate the formation of heterobinuclear complex species M₁M₂AB and M₁M₂A₂B in the pH range ~3.0-9.5, according to the following equilibria :

or

It is also clear from the speciation curves that formation of heterobimetallic complexes is preferred over the homobimetallic complexes.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that the overall stability constants of ternary metal complexes MAB in both the ratio (1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1) are in the following order :

And for quaternary M₁M₂AB (1 : 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 : 1) complexes the composite stability order is found to be :

In the present study M(II) is expected³ to bind with only two carboxyl groups of NTA in pyrocatechol mode and with one carboxyl and one amino groups of valine in glycine mode forming tetrahedral ternary complex. The carboxyl group and amino N of NTA can be utilized by other metal ion resulting in the formation of multimetal-multiligand complex. As a consequence the proposed structure for M(II)-NTA-valine system is supposed to be closer to that normally adopted in ternary complexes involved in process such as immobilized metal ion affinity chromatography (IMAC)⁴.

In the quaternary mixed ligand mixed metal systems under study involving NTA and valine there are two possibilities for the binding of NTA and valine with the metal ions. The first possibility is that one metal binds the ligand in pyrocatechol like mode and the other metal in a glycine like manner and vice-versa.

Experimental

All the ligands used were of A.R. grade. A nitrilotriacetic acid (0.01 M) solution was prepared by dissolving it into two equivalents of alkali (NaOH). Which was prepared in double distilled water. Metals nitrate solutions were prepared and standardized as described earlier⁵. pH measurements were made with a century model Cp 901 pH-meter using a special glass electrode (reproducibility ±0.01 pH). Equilibrium studies involved pH metric titration in aqueous medium keeping the concentration of the common ingredients identical in all the cases. The ratio of M₁ : M₂ : NTA : valine (1 : 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 : 1) and the total volume 50 ml. All the mixtures were titrated with carbonate free standard 0.1 M NaOH solution at a fixed temperature 30°C maintaining a fixed ionic strength I = 0.1 M NaNO₃.

Ionic product of water (K_w) at the experimental temperature and the activity coefficient of hydrogen ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from the literature⁶. Analytical concentrations of hydrogen ion corresponding to the pH meter reading were obtained by the usual procedure⁷. Formation constants (Table 1) were calculated using SCOGS computer program⁸.

Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of the species distribution curves (a representative curve has been shown in Fig. 1) obtained as computer output.

Fig. 1. Distribution curves of Cu^{II} Ni^{II} NTA valine 1 1 2 1 system (1) AH₃, (2) AH₂, (3) AH, (4) BH₂, (5) BH, (6) Cu(OH)⁺, (7) Cu(OH)₂, (8) Ni(OH)⁺, (9) Ni(OH)₂, (10) CuA, (11) NiA, (12) CuB, (13) NiB, (14) CuAB, (15) NiAB, (16) Cu₂A₂B, (17) Ni₂A₂B, (18) Cu-NiA₂B

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